

Strengthening BNI's Position as Transactional Bank by Optimization of Cash Management Solutions

Ringga Hasyella Harahap¹, Satya Adi Wibowo², Harimukti Wanderbori³

^{1,2,3} School of Business Management, Bandung Institute of Technology, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The cash management industry is becoming significantly intense from both banking and non-banking institutions as they keep innovating and offering advanced solutions to meet and cater to the dynamic business of the customers. This study was conducted to explore the strategic initiatives that can be formulated for PT. Bank Negara Indonesia (BNI) to strengthen its position as a transactional bank through the optimization of its cash management solutions, specifically focusing on BNIDirect. The analysis was carried out by understanding the nature of the competition and assessing the position of BNI in terms of cash management solutions relative to its competitors. The study used a qualitative method based on the interview with the key executive management and the literature review related to marketing and business strategy to uncover valuable insight and best practices that can strengthen the positions of BNI as a transactional bank. The research concludes that by addressing and overcoming the challenges that impacted cash management solutions, BNI can solidify its market position and achieve sustainable growth in the competitive cash management industry.

KEYWORDS: 7P's marketing mix, Generic Porter Strategy, PESTEL analysis, Porter's Five Forces, Transactional Banking, VRIO analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The succession of Indonesia Vision "Indonesia Emas 2045" requires comprehensive transformation efforts including significant advancements in the digital economy. This vision is aligned with BNI's transformation strategies in 2023 such as 1) developing transaction solutions and ecosystems to meet the needs of customers, 2) developing technological infrastructure and digital innovation through data-driven approaches based on analytics, customer experience, and expansion of partnerships and 3) increasing the collection of low-cost funds, known as the Current Account Saving Account (CASA). BNI is one of the top state-owned enterprises in the banking industry and plays a strategic role in strengthening its position in the transaction-based banking ecosystem. BNIDirect is presented as one of the BNI cash management platforms that is perceived as one indispensable tool that can support the achievement of those visions. In the dynamic business environment, the success of digital platforms is not merely determined by the sophistication or complexity of their features, but it is also crucially considered how to ensure the users are actively using the platforms. Therefore, the challenge faced by BNI is to increase the rate of active users in BNIDirect to strengthen its position as a transactional bank which plays a crucial role in supporting the successful implementation of transformation strategies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

To gain a comprehensive understanding of marketing and business strategy formulation, the author will use several foundational theories to enhance the comprehensiveness of the study. An overview of transactional banking and cash management perspectives is presented, pertinent to the discussion of BNI to strengthen its position in transactional scope. BNIDirect which is represented as cash management solutions became a central theme of this research that will cover the strategic role in optimizing cash flow management for corporate clients, the technological innovations implemented, customer satisfaction and adoption rates, and the competitive landscape in the cash management industry.

Transactional banking theory: Unlike traditional retail banking, which focuses on individual customers, transactional banking caters to the transactional needs of businesses, corporations, and institutional clients. A key offering in transactional banking is cash management. According to Ruth Wandhofer (2014), some banks have dedicated transaction banking divisions or branches, while others provide these services through various business segments like investment banking or corporate banking units.

Cash management theory: Cash management solutions are specialized services provided by banks, designed primarily for non-individual customers such as corporations, institutions, and other business entities. These services cover a wide range of transactional activities, including the management of incoming funds (cash in), efficient handling of liquidity to ensure cash availability and facilitation of outgoing payments (cash out). By leveraging cash management solutions, businesses can enhance their operational efficiency, gain better visibility into their finances, predict future cash flow patterns, and make informed strategic decisions. The transformation of cash management platforms through open banking is commonly implemented for some corporate and SME users. According to Arif A. Khan (2023), there are two ways for banks to leverage open banking opportunities:

Banking as a Platform: This approach provides customers with more financial and non-financial options, beneficial for banks by expanding their offerings through third-party partnerships.

Banking as a Service: This model accommodates fintech companies and other third parties, allowing them to connect with traditional bank systems through APIs to reach new markets.

Business-to-business marketing: B2B marketing involves promoting and selling products or services to other businesses by providing comprehensive solutions through mutual relationships, catering to the personalized needs of customers. It is nuanced and multifaceted, addressing the complex dynamics of business transactions. According to Kumar and Raheeja (2012), B2B refers to the exchange of goods or services between different business entities, such as transactions between a wholesaler and a retailer. In this research, B2B marketing focuses on the relationship between the bank and its corporate clients or SMEs.

Sustainable Banking: Banks and financial institutions must adhere to several rules regarding sustainable finance as outlined in OJK Regulation No. 51/POJK.03/2017, including sustainable finance involves a holistic approach to support the financial services sector in creating sustainable economic growth by aligning the interests of the economy, society, and the environment. b. The sustainability of financial products and services requires the integration of economic, social, and environmental aspects, along with governance features and their characteristics. The implementation of this regulation is not only to comply with OJK's strategic guidelines but also to consider environmental, social, and governance (ESG) concerns in decision-making processes. Consequently, these practices represent a responsible approach to capital allocation, risk management, and long-term economic development, aligning with sustainable objectives.

METHODOLOGY

The research in this study will be conducted using qualitative methods. The qualitative data will encompass comprehensive in-depth interviews primarily with the company's internal teams, enlightened by annual reports, journals, market analyses, and external media reports. Qualitative interviews involve the researcher conducting in-person interviews with the key management and selected customers to share their extensive understanding and knowledge relevant to the research objectives. Based on this qualitative data, the researcher will conduct further analysis which consists of external analysis such as Competitor & Customer analysis, PESTEL (Political, Economic, Sociocultural, Technological, Environmental, Legal) analysis and Porter 5's Forces (rivalry among competitors, buyer's bargaining power, supplier's bargaining power, threat of new entrant, threat of substitutes). Meanwhile, the internal analysis will be based on Resource analysis, VRIO (Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, Organized) analysis, Porter Value Chain, and STP (Segmentation, Targeting & Positioning).

RESULT & DISCUSSION

1. Internal analysis

A. Resource Analysis

Resource analysis will examine the tangible and intangible resources to achieve the strategic objectives. BNI can identify its strengths and understand its capabilities to build competitive advantages, which are crucial for optimizing BNI Direct as a cash management platform. This optimization will strengthen BNI's position as a transactional bank, as discussed below: Tangible resources will be assessing the organizational resources, physical resources & technological resources. Meanwhile, intangible resources will be analyzed based on the organizational resources, physical resources, and technological resources as follows:

Table 1. Tangible Resources

Tangible Resources	
Organizational Resources	Implementation of a new way of working (NWOW) which results in division separation that divides the function of channel and business division, named as Wholesale Digital Channel (WDC) Division and Wholesale Product & Partnership Division.
Physical Resources	Cash Management Platforms such as BNIDirect, e-Collection, Debit VA, Financial Supply Chain Management (FSCM), Garansi Bank Online.
Technological Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Open Banking through API ▪ Operational Data Store (ODS) ▪ COBIT 5 framework ▪ Disaster Recovery Center (DRC) ▪ International Organization for Standardization 9001 (ISO 9001)

Table 2. Intangible Resources

Intangible Resources	
Human Resources	Advisors in the Wholesale Product Partnership Division are certified by some relevant certifications such as Certificate in International Trade and Finance (CITF), Badan Sertifikasi Manajemen Risiko (BSMR) and also wholesale transaction banking program brevet. This certification is to ensure that employees are equipped with sufficient knowledge to provide the customer with expert advice and develop effective solutions.
Innovation Resources	Nurturing and cultivating continuous innovation practices such as BNI Innovation (Binnova) for the internal environment and Hackathon Festival for the external environment.
Reputational Resources	Recently, BNIDirect as one of the cash management solutions awarded by Euromoney Cash Management Survey 2023 dan Alpha Southeast Asia Awards 2023

By analyzing its tangible and intangible resources, BNI can identify its capabilities, which serve as the foundation for creating unique value propositions. This differentiation increases BNI's competitive advantages. A comprehensive understanding of its resources and capabilities allows BNI to strategically harness strengths, address weaknesses, and explore opportunities to optimize and increase the activation rate of BNIDirect, ensuring it meets customers' diverse financing needs.

B. VRIO Analysis

By examining the VRIO Analysis, BNI can identify resources that provide a sustainable competitive advantage and areas needing improvement. Insights from this analysis will guide strategic decisions to enhance BNIDirect's market position, ensuring customer needs are accurately met and outperforming competitors with innovative cash management platforms.

Table. 3 VRIO Analysis

Resource Of Capability	Valuable	Rare	Imitation Costly	Organized to capture Value	Competitive Advantage
Brand Reputation	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Sustainable Competitive advantages
Technology Advancement	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Sustainable Competitive advantages
Feature Complexity	Yes	No	Yes	No	Temporary Competitive Advantage
Employee expertise	Yes	No	Yes	No	Temporary Competitive Advantage
Customer Service excellence	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Temporary Competitive Advantage
Innovation culture	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Sustainable Competitive Advantage

C. Porter Value Chain Analysis

Porter Value Chain Primary activities will consist of two activities such as Primary activities and Secondary activities. Primary activities are the main processes involved in the creation, production, marketing, and delivering the product. Meanwhile, secondary activities in value chain analysis are the support processes that are not involved in the production.

Primary Activities consist of:

Inbound Logistics: In the banking industry, inbound logistics involve the collection of funds and capital. For cash management, this means prioritizing cheap funds based on CASA (Current Account & Saving Account) through transactions conducted on BNIDirect for Current Accounts and BNI Mobile Banking for Savings Accounts. BNI aims to convert inactive users into active ones, as active cash management users can generate an average growth of approximately 17.1% annually.

Operations: BNI's core operations in the business banking sector include platforms such as BNIDirect, e-Collection, Debit VA, Financial Supply Chain Management (FSCM), and Garansi Bank Online. These platforms generate fee-based income, which reached IDR 363 billion in 2022, a 17.9% increase from 2021. This growth was driven by customer activities related to transfers, foreign exchange transactions, and payments through the State Revenue Module (MPN).

Outbound Logistics: To ensure effective distribution of cash management solutions, BNI equipped BNIDirect with features like account statements, transaction notifications, and electronic bank statements (EBS). These tools facilitate seamless and efficient service delivery, helping customers manage their financial transactions proactively.

Secondary activities consist of:

Human Resource Management: BNI views human capital as its greatest asset, providing equal opportunities for employee training and development. With approximately 27,000 employees and 237,000 training participants, BNI ensures continuous skill and knowledge enhancement to drive growth and success.

Technology Development: BNI collaborates with fintech to create digital banking innovations, enhancing customer experience through platforms like BNIDirect. With over 4,000 partners and 280 API services, BNI's Open API supports integrated financial solutions and expands CASA collection.

Procurement: BNI's Electronic Procurement (e-Proc) platform digitalizes procurement processes, covering modules such as procurement management, vendor management, contract management, and payment management. This ensures efficient, transparent, and accountable processes, aligning with stakeholder interests and GCG principles

D. STP Analysis

BNI has strategically segmented its market for BNIDirect, targeting non-individual customers across four key segments such as Wholesale & International Banking, Institutional Banking, Enterprises & Commercial Banking and Retail Banking. By focusing on promising sectors within each segment, BNI aims to optimize growth and profitability, reinforcing its market position in the cash management industry based on the current targets below:

Table. 4 Current Target

Targeting	
Wholesale & International Banking	Establishing priority sectors that have a positive impact on increasing potential market share, credit asset quality, and profitability for BNI, including the energy, agribusiness, manufacturing, telecommunications, and digital economy sectors.
Institutional Banking	Optimizing state budget funds (APBN) distributed to Ministries, Agencies, Universities, and Public Service Agencies (BLU) / Work Units (Satker)
Enterprise & Commercial Banking	Focus on sustainable growth of low-cost funds by increasing the number of account executions and enhancing funds sourced from customers' family trees.
Retail Banking	targeting on payroll services, professionals, and business owners. This selective approach aims to address their specific financial transaction needs with customized solutions.

E. 7P's Marketing Mix

BNIDirect which is presented as BNI's primary platform for cash management solutions, offers three main services: payment management, liquidity management, and collection management. Payment management includes features like e-tax, transfer management, and billing & utilities payment, streamlining various financial transactions for customers. Liquidity management ensures optimal cash flow through cash pooling and cash distribution. Collection management, with

virtual accounts and auto debit features, simplifies fund collection. BNIDirect charges competitive prices per feature, typically ranging from Rp. 1,000 to Rp. 5,000 per transaction, tailored to business complexity. The digital platform is accessible via mobile and web, providing convenience and security for customers. Promotion is achieved through dedicated relationship managers, advisory staff, and a strong presence on social media and traditional media. Customer service staff play a crucial role in maintaining customer relationships, while collaboration among various divisions ensures effective problem-solving and solution delivery. The user-friendly interface and positive customer testimonials further enhance BNIDirect's credibility and branding as a reliable cash management tool.

2. External analysis

A. PESTEL Analysis

Indonesia's political landscape is pivotal for economic growth, with President Jokowi Widodo targeting 90% financial inclusion by 2024. BNI can leverage government strategies to enhance BNIDirect's reach, benefiting from policies that improve access to formal financial services, boost financial literacy, and expand digital financial services. Indonesia's economy, resilient amidst political changes, grew by 5.11% in early 2024, with the digital economy projected to rise significantly. Socioculturally, increasing internet penetration and positive consumer sentiment towards digital banking indicate a promising future. Technologically, innovations like open banking and API integration enhance financial solutions, while environmentally, digital banking reduces paper usage, supporting sustainability goals. Legally, BNI complies with regulations promoting digital banking, ensuring financial inclusion and customer data security, solidifying its position in Indonesia's digital financial ecosystem.

B. Competitor Analysis

The competitor analysis of BNI's cash management solutions compared to BCA, Mandiri, and BRI reveals distinct strategies and performance metrics. BNIDirect, BNI's primary platform, offers a range of services including payment, liquidity, and collection management. Competitors like Qlola and Kopra have integrated single sign-on (SSO) features, providing streamlined access to various financial services, enhancing customer experience. BCA's cash management focuses on payable, receivable, and liquidity management. BNIDirect charges transaction fees ranging from Rp. 1,000 to Rp. 5,000, while some competitors offer free services. All platforms are accessible via web and mobile, with strong digital marketing and customer service teams underpinning their operations. BNI's cash management user base grew at a CAGR of 27%, lagging behind BRI (34%), Mandiri (37%), and BCA (49%). In terms of transaction volume, Mandiri led with Rp. 18,567 trillion in 2022, and BCA exhibited the highest CAGR of 49%. BNI needs to enhance BNIDirect's utilization, possibly by integrating SSO features, to compete more effectively. Mandiri's success in corporate transactions and BCA's ability to attract a large user base highlight areas for BNI to improve its strategic approach and customer acquisition efforts.

C. Customer Analysis

Based on customer interviews, BNIDirect should become more customer-centric by tailoring transaction features to specific customer needs and simplifying the access process to enhance user experience. Customer perceptions across the 7P's indicate a preference for integrated and customizable platforms, competitive and flexible pricing, web-based access, more loyalty programs, and efficient, knowledgeable staff. Users value intuitive app features and detailed guidance. Customer analysis shows that the majority of BNIDirect users are inactive, with only a slight increase in active users from 13% to 17% between December 2023 and May 2024. The transfer feature is the most utilized, indicating a need for BNI to maintain and optimize this function. To improve performance, BNI should unify cash management platforms to increase active user rates, address customer feedback, and continuously enhance platform reliability. By focusing on these areas, BNI can boost customer satisfaction, loyalty, and solidify its position as a leading transactional bank.

D. Porter 5's forces

BNI can strengthen its position as a transactional bank by examining and optimizing its cash management solutions using Porter's Five Forces approach: buyer's bargaining power, supplier's bargaining power, threat of new entrants, threat of substitutes, and rivalry among competitors.

- **Buyer's Bargaining Power**
In the B2B cash management industry, corporate and SME customers wield significant bargaining power, requiring feature customization and competitive pricing. BNI should expand its coverage and assign relevant product specialists to understand and meet customer needs, enhancing customer stickiness and engagement.
- **Supplier's Bargaining Power**
BNI relies on IT service providers to support its banking activities. Regulations require BNI to follow specific procedures for new products, which can slow innovation. Partnering with a growing number of IT service providers offers BNI flexibility and low switching costs, enabling efficient and effective customer solutions.
- **Threat of New Entrants**
High initial investments and regulatory compliance deter new entrants in the cash management industry. Existing banks like BNI benefit from established ecosystems supporting their performance. BNI mitigates this threat through continuous innovation and strategic partnerships, fostering internal and external innovation via events like BINNOVA and BNI Hackfest.
- **Threat of Substitutes**
Competitors offering similar cash management solutions increase the risk of substitutes. BNI must maintain strong customer relationships and an agile, innovative approach, collaborating with fintechs to enhance BNIDirect. Ensuring the platform's reliability and adapting to customer needs helps retain customers and strengthen BNI's brand as a leading transactional bank.
- **Rivalry among Competitors**
Intense competition with low product differentiation and low switching costs requires BNI to create unique value propositions. Offering personalized customer experience managers, seamless integration with ERP/SAP systems through APIs, and customized financial dashboards can enhance customer engagement and loyalty.

3. SWOT Analysis

After conducting internal and external analyses, a SWOT analysis will be performed to identify strategic initiatives for enhancing BNI's market presence with BNIDirect as a cash management platform. This improvement aims to boost the activation rate of BNIDirect users. The SWOT analysis will examine the strengths and weaknesses of BNI's cash management solution (internal factors) and the opportunities and threats in the cash management industry (external factors).

A. Strengths

BNIDirect has several strengths that can be leveraged to achieve strategic goals in the cash management industry:

- **Brand Reputation (S1)**
BNI cash management solutions received many awards from institutions such as Euromoney, Alpha Southeast Asia, and Asia Money.
- **Open API Services (S2)**
BNI's extensive Open API network, with over 4,000 partners and 280 API services, enables comprehensive digital platforms and integrated financial solutions.
- **Technological Advancements (S3)**
BNI's investment in data-driven analytics, customer experience, and expanding partnerships aligns with Bank Indonesia's 2025 blueprint, ensuring it stays current with digital banking trends.
- **Innovation Culture (S4)**
The implementation of the New Way of Working (NWOW) promotes a leaner, more agile, and customer-centric approach, fostering continuous product and service innovation.

B. Weaknesses

Identifying and addressing weaknesses is crucial for improving cash management's performance:

- **Customer Acquisition and Market Share (W1)**
There is a lack of tight supervision from portfolio owners, leading to suboptimal customer acquisition and market share growth, particularly in the downstream business.

- **Complexity of Features (W2)**
While comprehensive, the complexity of BNIDirect's features can be overwhelming, making it difficult for customers to navigate and use the platform effectively.
- **Platform Reliability (W3)**
Occasional downtime and disruptions can significantly impact customer satisfaction and trust, highlighting the need for improved platform reliability.

C. Opportunities

Exploiting external opportunities can help BNI enhance its cash management performance:

- **Digital Economy and Financial Inclusion (O1)**
Positive trends in the digital economy and financial inclusion, supported by government regulations, present opportunities for growth and sustainability in digital transactions.
- **Digital Literacy (O2)**
Increasing digital literacy in Indonesia, with a rising index score from 3.49 in 2021 to a projected 3.65 in 2023, indicates a growing capability among citizens to use information and communication technology effectively.
- **Open Banking (O3)**
Bank Indonesia's 2025 blueprint emphasizes Open Banking, which will drive digital transformation and innovative transaction solutions, enhancing financial inclusion and user experience.

D. Threats

Mitigating external threats is essential for maintaining performance in cash management

- **Fintech Competition (T1)**
The rise of fintech companies offering similar cash management solutions poses a threat to BNI, necessitating quick adaptation to secure market share.
- **Cybercrimes (T2)**
Cybercrimes such as fraud, data theft, social engineering, and money laundering can damage BNI's reputation and erode consumer trust in digital platforms.
- **Global Uncertainty (T3)**
Political instability and financial crises can negatively impact consumer purchasing power, reducing financial transactions and affecting BNI's performance.

4. TOWS Matrix

The TOWS Matrix provides strategic initiatives by leveraging BNI's strengths, addressing weaknesses, capitalizing on opportunities, and mitigating threats to strengthen BNIDirect's market presence as a cash management platform.

A. SO Strategies (Strength-Opportunities)

These strategies leverage BNI's strengths to capitalize on external opportunities:

- **SO1:** Utilize API services to customize cash management solutions to meet specific customer needs and ecosystems, creating a more flexible and positive user experience.
- **SO2:** Optimize digital technology advancements like AI, data analytics, biometrics, cloud computing, and IoT to create more efficient, secure, and user-friendly services. AI can automate and improve decision-making, data analytics can provide valuable cash flow insights, and biometrics can simplify authentication processes.

B. WO Strategies (Weakness-Opportunities)

These strategies aim to overcome weaknesses by taking advantage of external opportunities:

- **WO1:** Develop integrated monitoring tools for portfolio owners to track customer performance and value chains, enhancing productivity and business potential optimization through advanced analytics.
- **WO2:** Simplify access to cash management platforms using single sign-on (SSO) technology, increasing customer satisfaction by allowing seamless access to multiple platforms without repeated credential entries. This can also reduce downtime and resource allocation for more reliable services.

C. ST Strategies (Strength-Threats)

These strategies use BNI's strengths to mitigate external threats:

- **ST1:** Collaborate with fintech companies to acquire new customers and boost the activation rate of existing customers. This partnership can introduce innovative business schemes and add value to BNIDirect's features.
- **ST2:** Ensure that all cash management innovations align with Bank Indonesia's Blueprint to mitigate risks and enhance credibility and consumer trust.

D. WT Strategies (Weakness-Threats)

These strategies address weaknesses while mitigating external threats:

- **WT1:** Establish strategic partnerships with fintechs for knowledge transfer and mutual learning. Joint R&D projects can help innovate and improve BNIDirect's features to stay competitive.
- **WT2:** Ensure all business processes in cash management solutions adhere to standard operating procedures (SOPs), maintaining high security levels and protecting BNI and its customers from potential legal issues.

BUSINESS SOLUTION

A. Marketing Strategy Formulation

▪ Proposed 7P's Marketing Mix

To align with customer needs and digital trends, BNI should unify its various cash management solutions—BNIDirect, FSCM, BNI FX, GB Online, E-Collection, and Trade & Finance services—into one integrated platform with SSO access, enhancing convenience and streamlining transactions. Competitive pricing schemes should reflect standard operating procedures while a flexible pricing framework ensures prompt decisions based on the customer profitability analysis. BNIDirect must be accessible across various devices and operating systems, providing a consistent user experience. To enhance awareness and solidify its position, BNI should organize annual business events with industry leaders, adding value through mentorship and resources. Fostering a culture of militancy among portfolio owners will improve networking and customer relationships, supported by collaboration-driven KPIs to minimize silo attitudes. New sales models and channels focused on customer engagement, like the "branch of the future," will facilitate the shift to digital transactions. Physical elements like customized hard tokens and VA Debit Cards will reinforce brand identity and enhance customer satisfaction.

▪ Proposed STP

BNI's current segmentation effectively divides customers based on their group entities and industries, optimizing cash management solutions and reinforcing BNI's position as a transactional bank. Targeting focuses on priority sectors within each segment, with a proposed strategy to enhance growth and engagement. BNIDirect is positioned as a customizable one-stop transactional platform for multi-segment customers, serving as the cornerstone of transactional banking and facilitating sustainable transactions and optimal cross-selling. This strategic positioning aims to establish BNIDirect as a comprehensive and competitive digital ecosystem in the cash management industry, supporting BNI's goal of being the transaction bank of choice for customers.

B. Business Strategy Formulation

BNI's business strategy for the BNIDirect platform will follow Porter's generic strategy of integrated cost leadership and differentiation. This approach aims to provide unique and valuable transactional banking services while maintaining a competitive cost structure. Leveraging advanced technology and centralized decision-making, BNI will implement two strategic initiatives: 1) Customized pricing tailored for specific customers, automatically set on BNIDirect and other cash management platforms based on customer profitability analysis, and 2) Integration of BNIDirect with other cash management platforms into a comprehensive system. These initiatives will enable BNI to offer high-quality services at a lower cost, encouraging increased usage of cash management services. Additionally, by developing innovative approaches and personalized value-added customer experiences, BNI can differentiate its offerings to meet diverse customer needs, attract new customers, enhance satisfaction, boost active user rates, and maintain a strong competitive market position, ultimately leading to sustainable growth and profitability.

CONCLUSION

Effective cash flow management is essential for companies to maintain financial health and achieve long-term success, as it helps them manage cash inflow, liquidity, and cash outflow efficiently. The increasing demand for cash management solutions is evident from the performance of top banks like Mandiri, BCA, BNI, and BRI. Strong cash management solutions enable banks to improve their transactional banking capabilities, increase low-cost fund collections (CASA), and boost Fee-Based Income (FBI). To strengthen its position, BNI should focus on three key areas: increasing active users on its cash management platforms, especially BNIDirect, by leveraging portfolio owners to target customer segments effectively; simplifying transaction processes to enhance customer satisfaction with convenient, reliable, and appropriately featured platforms; and developing a unique value proposition through swift decision-making and streamlined business processes, which will differentiate BNI in the competitive market and drive sustained growth and profitability.

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